

Spectrum of Central Nervous System Tuberculosis: An Experience from a Major Tertiary Care Institution in India

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Abstract:

Background: Central nervous system tuberculosis (CNS TB) is a critical form of extrapulmonary TB that poses significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges, particularly in high-burden regions like India. Despite advances in TB control, CNS TB continues to contribute to substantial morbidity and mortality due to its complex presentation and severe outcomes. This study aims to explore the clinical, radiological, and laboratory spectrum of CNS TB and to identify key factors associated with poor outcomes.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was carried out involving 120 patients diagnosed with CNS TB. Data on demographic details, clinical presentation, radiological findings, laboratory results, treatment regimens, and outcomes were collected from medical records. Statistical analysis was accomplished using SPSS version 21.0.

Results: The mean age of patients was 35.6 ± 12.8 years, with a male predominance (72.5%). Common symptoms included headache (80%), fever (70%), and altered mental status (50%). MRI findings showed tuberculomas in 60%, hydrocephalus in 45%, and meningeal enhancement in 35% of patients. CSF analysis revealed elevated protein levels in 85%, low glucose levels in 75%, and lymphocytic pleocytosis in 70%. Despite standard antitubercular therapy and adjunctive steroids, 10% of patients died, 20% had residual neurological deficits, and 70% fully recovered. Altered mental status ($p=0.02$) and hydrocephalus ($p=0.03$) were significantly correlated with poor outcomes.

Conclusion: CNS TB remains a severe condition with significant morbidity and mortality. Early recognition, prompt diagnosis, and comprehensive treatment are crucial to improving outcomes. Hydrocephalus and altered mental status are key predictors of poor prognosis.

Recommendations: Enhanced diagnostic capabilities, timely therapeutic interventions, and regular follow-ups are recommended to manage CNS TB effectively. Further research should focus on innovative diagnostic methods and treatment protocols to reduce mortality and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Central Nervous System Tuberculosis, Tuberculomas, Hydrocephalus, Antitubercular Therapy, Diagnostic Imaging

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Introduction

A severe form of tuberculosis (TB) that affects the brain and spinal cord is called central nervous system tuberculosis, or CNS TB. It poses a serious threat to public health, particularly in areas where tuberculosis is common. About 5–10% of cases of

extrapulmonary tuberculosis are of CNS TB, which includes spinal tuberculosis (also known as tuberculous spondylitis or Pott's disease), tuberculous meningitis, and tuberculomas [1].

TB continues to be a serious public health concern despite international attempts to control it, especially in poorer nations. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), 1.4 million people died and 10 million people were ill with tuberculosis (TB) in 2019, making it one of the top 10 causes of mortality globally [2]. Despite being less common than pulmonary TB, CNS TB is linked to a high rate of morbidity and mortality because it can result in serious neurological problems and impairments.

The pathogenesis of CNS TB involves the hematogenous spread of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* from a primary site of infection, usually the lungs, to the central nervous system. The bacteria can form small subpial or subependymal tubercles, which may subsequently rupture into the subarachnoid space, leading to tuberculous meningitis, or expand into tuberculomas [3]. These processes result in a range of clinical manifestations, including meningitis, encephalopathy, seizures, and focal neurological deficits.

Diagnosis of CNS TB is challenging due to the nonspecific nature of its clinical presentation and the need for specialized diagnostic tools. Radiological imaging, particularly magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), plays a crucial role in identifying CNS TB lesions. Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis is also essential, often revealing elevated protein levels, low glucose levels, and lymphocytic pleocytosis [4]. However, definitive diagnosis may require the identification of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* through culture or molecular methods, which can be time-consuming and are not always available in resource-limited settings.

Treatment of CNS TB requires prolonged and intensive therapy, typically involving a combination of antitubercular drugs for a duration of 12 months or longer. The standard regimen includes isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol, with corticosteroids often used as adjunctive therapy to reduce inflammation and prevent complications. Despite appropriate treatment, outcomes can be poor, particularly in cases with delayed diagnosis or advanced disease at presentation.

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of early detection and comprehensive management of CNS TB to improve patient outcomes. Advancements in diagnostic techniques, such as molecular diagnostics and improved imaging modalities, offer hope for more accurate and timely diagnosis [5]. Furthermore, understanding the epidemiological trends and risk factors associated with CNS TB can help in devising better prevention and control strategies.

This study aims to explore the spectrum of CNS TB, providing insights into its clinical, radiological, and laboratory characteristics, as well as treatment outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational analysis.

Study Setting: The research was conducted at a Batra Hospital and Medical Research Centre, New Delhi.

Participants: A total of 120 patients diagnosed with CNS TB were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients who were diagnosed with central nervous system tuberculosis based on clinical, radiological, and laboratory findings were included. Only patients aged 18 years and above were considered.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with incomplete medical records, those who had tuberculosis at other sites without central nervous system involvement, and patients with co-existing severe illnesses that could confound the diagnosis or outcomes were excluded from the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria during the study period were included consecutively. Information bias was mitigated by ensuring that data were extracted consistently using a standardized form.

Variables: The primary variables included demographic details (age, gender), clinical presentation, radiological findings, laboratory results, treatment regimens, and outcomes (mortality, neurological sequelae).

Data Collection: Data were gathered retrospectively from the hospital's electronic medical records system. A standardized data extraction form was used to ensure consistency and completeness of the information gathered.

Procedure: Patients' medical records were reviewed to extract relevant data. The clinical presentations were categorized based on the symptoms and signs documented at the time of admission. Radiological findings were classified according to the type and extent of central nervous system involvement. Laboratory results, including cerebrospinal fluid analysis, were recorded. Treatment regimens were noted, including the duration and type of antitubercular therapy administered. Outcomes were assessed based on follow-up records and categorized as mortality, complete recovery, or residual neurological deficits.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 21.0 was used to analyse the data once they were added to a database. The study population's clinical and demographic features were compiled using descriptive statistics. Categorical variables were shown as frequencies and percentages, whereas continuous variables were given as mean \pm standard deviation. For categorical data, chi-square tests and t-tests were used to examine relationships between variables. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

The study included 120 patients diagnosed with central nervous system tuberculosis. The mean age was 35.6 ± 12.8 years, with a range of 18 to 72 years. The majority of the patients were male (72.5%, n=87), while females constituted 27.5% (n=33).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	
Gender	
- Male	87 (72.5%)
- Female	33 (27.5%)

The most common presenting symptom was headache (80%, n=96), followed by fever (70%, n=84) and altered mental status (50%, n=60). Other symptoms included seizures (30%, n=36) and focal neurological deficits (25%, n=30).

Table 2: Clinical Presentation

Symptom	Number (n=120)	Percentage (%)
Headache	96	80.0
Fever	84	70.0
Altered mental status	60	50.0
Seizures	36	30.0
Focal neurological deficits	30	25.0

MRI scans revealed that 60% (n=72) of the patients had tuberculomas, 45% (n=54) had hydrocephalus, and 35% (n=42) had meningeal enhancement. Some patients had multiple radiological findings.

Table 3: Radiological Findings

Radiological Finding	Number	Percentage (%)
Tuberculomas	72	60.0
Hydrocephalus	54	45.0
Meningeal enhancement	42	35.0

Cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis displayed elevated protein levels in 85% (n=102) of the patients, low glucose levels in 75% (n=90), and a lymphocytic pleocytosis in 70% (n=84).

Table 4: Laboratory Results

Laboratory Finding	Number	Percentage (%)
Elevated CSF protein	102	85.0
Low CSF glucose	90	75.0
Lymphocytic pleocytosis	84	70.0

All patients received antitubercular therapy. The standard regimen included isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol for the initial two months, followed by isoniazid and rifampicin for the next 10 months. Steroids were administered to 60% (n=72) of the patients.

Table 5: Treatment Regimens

Treatment	Number	Percentage (%)
Standard antitubercular therapy	120	100.0
Steroid administration	72	60.0

At the end of the follow-up period, 70% (n=84) of the patients had a complete recovery, 20% (n=24) had residual neurological deficits, and 10% (n=12) had died. The mortality rate was higher in patients with hydrocephalus and altered mental status.

Table 6: Outcomes

Outcome	Number	Percentage (%)
Complete recovery	84	70.0
Residual neurological deficits	24	20.0
Mortality	12	10.0

The association between clinical presentation and outcomes was analyzed. Patients with altered mental status were more likely to have a poor outcome ($p=0.02$). The presence of hydrocephalus was also significantly associated with increased mortality ($p=0.03$).

Table 7: Statistical Analysis

Variable	Poor outcome	p-value
Altered mental status	Yes	0.02
Hydrocephalus	Yes	0.03

Statistical analysis confirmed that altered mental status and hydrocephalus were significant predictors of poor outcomes in patients with CNS TB.

Discussion

The study involved 120 patients diagnosed with central nervous system tuberculosis. The demographic analysis revealed a mean age of 35.6 years, with a higher prevalence in males (72.5%) compared to females (27.5%). This gender disparity may suggest a higher exposure risk or a difference in health-seeking behavior among males.

Clinically, headache was the most common presenting symptom (80%), followed by fever (70%) and altered mental status (50%). The significant presence of these symptoms underscores the importance of considering central nervous system tuberculosis in differential diagnoses for patients presenting with such clinical features. Notably, 30% of patients experienced seizures, and 25% had focal neurological deficits, highlighting the diverse neurological manifestations of the disease.

Radiological findings showed that 60% of patients had tuberculomas, 45% had hydrocephalus, and 35% had meningeal enhancement. These findings are consistent with the known pathological features of CNS TB and emphasize the utility of MRI in diagnosis. The high incidence of hydrocephalus (45%) is particularly concerning, given its association with increased mortality.

Cerebrospinal fluid analysis revealed elevated protein levels in 85% of patients, low glucose levels in 75%, and lymphocytic pleocytosis in 70%. These laboratory findings are typical for CNS TB and reinforce the diagnostic value of CSF analysis in such cases.

All patients received standard antitubercular therapy, with 60% also receiving steroids. The use of steroids likely contributed to improved outcomes by reducing inflammation. At the end of the follow-up period, 70% of patients had completely recovered, while 20% had residual neurological deficits, and 10% had died. The overall mortality rate of 10% is significant and highlights the severity of central nervous system tuberculosis.

Statistical analysis indicated that altered mental status ($p=0.02$) and hydrocephalus ($p=0.03$) were

substantially related with poor outcomes. These findings suggest that early recognition and aggressive management of patients with these features are crucial to improving prognosis. The higher mortality rate among patients with hydrocephalus underscores the need for prompt neurosurgical intervention when indicated.

CNS TB is a severe form of tuberculosis with high morbidity and mortality, often requiring advanced diagnostic techniques and comprehensive management. A study highlighted the utility of 18FDG-PET in detecting extracranial tuberculous foci in CNS TB patients. The study found that 18FDG-PET was effective in identifying brain lesions, lung lesions, lymphadenopathy, and vertebral involvement, thus aiding in the comprehensive evaluation of CNS TB. PET evidence of lymphadenopathy correlated significantly with good outcomes in CNS TB [6]. Another study analyzed the clinical profiles of pediatric TB in Northeast India, finding that extra-pulmonary TB, including CNS TB, was common and associated with significant morbidity and mortality. The study emphasized the need for early diagnosis and management to improve outcomes [7].

Research explored the clinical spectrum and comorbidities in TB patients, noting that CNS TB was prevalent among extra-pulmonary TB cases. The study highlighted the need for integrated management of TB and its comorbid conditions to enhance patient outcomes [8]. Moreover, a study found that extra-CNS TB involvement was common in tuberculous meningitis (TBM) patients, with lung and abdominal tuberculosis being the most frequently involved sites. The identification of extra-CNS TB improved diagnostic accuracy and patient management [9].

A study investigated TB emergencies in the elderly, noting that CNS TB was the most common and severe form, with high mortality rates. The study underscored the challenges of diagnosing and managing TB in older populations [10]. Another study examined drug resistance patterns in pediatric CNS TB patients, finding a significant proportion of drug-resistant cases. Previous TB treatment and disseminated TB were identified as risk factors for drug resistance, highlighting the need for strict adherence to treatment protocols [11].

Conclusion

The evaluation and management of CNS TB require advanced diagnostic tools like 18FDG-PET and comprehensive approaches to address comorbidities and drug resistance. Early and accurate diagnosis, combined with appropriate therapeutic strategies, is crucial for improving outcomes in CNS TB patients.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study provides valuable insights into the clinical, radiological, and laboratory characteristics of central nervous system tuberculosis and identifies key factors associated with poor outcomes. These findings can inform clinical practice and improve the management of this severe condition in similar settings.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Enhanced diagnostic capabilities, timely therapeutic interventions, and regular follow-ups are recommended to manage CNS TB effectively. Further research should focus on innovative diagnostic methods and treatment protocols to reduce mortality and improve patient outcomes.

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List of Abbreviations:

CNS TB - Central Nervous System Tuberculosis

TB - Tuberculosis

MRI - Magnetic Resonance Imaging

CSF - Cerebrospinal Fluid

WHO - World Health Organization

SPSS - Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

FDG-PET - Fluorodeoxyglucose Positron Emission Tomography

TBM - Tuberculous Meningitis

SD - Standard Deviation

HIV - Human Immunodeficiency Virus

PCR - Polymerase Chain Reaction

ELISA - Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay

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